

THE SYMBOLISM OF PROPHETS IN NODIRA'S GHAZAL

Barno Abdurahmonova

Associate Professor at Kokand State University

Annotation: The article examines the artistic use of prophetic imagery and the literary device of allusion (*talmeh*) in the classical poetry of Mohlaroyim Nodira. Focusing on one of her well-known ghazals, the author explores how Nodira integrates religious figures like Solomon (Sulaymon) and Sufi symbols like Shaykh San'on to express the pain of separation and philosophical reflections on life's impermanence. The study highlights the poetess's mastery of combining *talmeh* with other literary devices such as antithesis (*tazod*), metaphor (*istiora*), and proverbial reference (*irsoli masal*).

Keywords: Nodira, ghazal, *talmeh* (allusion), Prophet Solomon, Shaykh San'on, Sufism, classical poetry, literary devices, antithesis, metaphor.

Аннотация: В данной статье рассматривается художественное использование образов пророков и литературоведческого приема аллюзии (*талмех*) в классическом наследии Мохларойим Нодир. На примере одного из ее знаменитых газелей автор анализирует, как поэтесса использует образы пророка Сулеймана и Шейха Санъона для выражения боли разлуки и философских размышлений о бренности мира. Особое внимание уделяется мастерству Нодир в гармоничном сочетании приема *талмех* с другими средствами художественной выразительности, такими как антитеза (*тазод*), метафора и ирсоли масал.

Ключевые слова: Нодира, газель, талмех (аллюзия), пророк Сулейман, Шейх Санъон, суфизм, классическая поэзия, литературные приемы, антитеза, метафора.

In the history of our classical literature, all writers created remarkable examples of the art of allusion (*talmeh*) in their poetry by referring to the names of prophets, famous historical figures, legendary heroes, and even place names. In poetry, the reference to historical events and figures, as well as literary characters, is known as the art of allusion (*talmeh*). This term, which in Arabic conveys meanings such as “the flashing of lightning,” “casting a glance,” or “looking briefly,” enables poets to avoid explaining an intended idea in detail or describing a situation extensively. Instead, they can achieve the desired effect simply by referring to another real-life or literary fact that corresponds to the intended idea or situation. As a result, a great deal of meaning can be expressed with few words, since the content of a verse employing *talmeh* becomes enriched through its connection with the historical event or literary work being alluded to [1]. This literary device has been widely studied by many scholars. The renowned scholar Atoullouh Husayniy defines it in his work *Badoye us-sanoyi* as follows: “*Talmeh* is the act of referring in speech to a famous story, a well-known poem, or a popular proverb.” [2].

The use of *talmeh* in the works of Mohlaroyim Nodira also occupies a leading position among other literary devices. In the poetess's works, *talmeh* appears frequently, particularly in poems devoted to the theme of separation. One notable example is the ghazal beginning with the line, “*Vasl uyin obod qildim buzdi hijron oqibat*” (“I built the house of union, yet separation ultimately destroyed it”). From the very first couplet of this ghazal, it is not difficult to understand that the central idea reflects the suffering of a woman separated from her spouse. The marriage of Nodira and Umarxon was founded upon mutual love. With the modesty and grace characteristic of Uzbek women, the poetess expressed her love and respect for her husband through poetry.

The literary device of contrast (*tazod*) is widely employed throughout the ghazal. This can be observed even in the opening couplet, where concepts such as *union (visol)* and *separation (hijron)*, as well as *prosperity (obod)* and *ruin (vayron)*, are deliberately contrasted. The incurable wound of love in the poetess's heart is openly revealed. In nearly all the couplets of the ghazal, Nodira skillfully makes use of antithesis (*tazod*) to intensify emotional expression.

In Nodira's poetry, particularly in poems enriched with Sufi symbols and imagery, *talmeh* is employed purposefully and effectively. The figure of the sheikh who falls in love with a Christian maiden (*Tarso qizi*) is widely used by poets as an allusive reference. Likewise, Nodira turns to the images of Shaykh San'on and Solomon (*Sulaymon*) to convey her intended meaning. This clearly demonstrates Nodira's familiarity with Sufi teachings and spiritual thought. In Nodira's literary works, this finds its interpretation as follows:

**Zohido, ishq-u muhabbat ahlini ma'zur tut
Yor ko'yida na bo'ldi Shayx San'on oqibat.**

During the course of her philosophical reflections, Nodira frequently refers to the names of prophets, sheikhs, saints, Sufis, rulers, poets, and scholars. As noted above, the most frequently encountered figures in her ghazals are the images of prophets. This phenomenon is closely connected with the influence of Islam, particularly the Qur'an and other sacred religious texts. Literary scholar Mahbuba Qodirova writes: "Widowed in her thirties, the poetess sought consolation during those sorrowful days by spiritually remaining close to her late husband and drawing comfort from the verses of the Qur'an and the teachings of the hadiths of Prophet Muhammad" [3]. The truth embodied in this observation can also be found in the couplets of the ghazal under discussion. In expressing her emotions and philosophical reflections, Nodira turns to these figures while portraying the experiences of the lyrical protagonist, the appearance of the beloved, and various qualities attributed to him.:

**Garchi bor edi musaxxar devlar farmonida
Poymol xayli mo'r o'ldi Sulaymon oqibat**

This couplet alludes to the Prophet Solomon (*Sulaymon*).

The poetess portrays the psychological state of a woman separated from her spouse, deeply experiencing her thoughts and emotional suffering. She expresses the pain of a heart consumed by the agony of separation through the folk expression equivalent to "my heart bled," symbolizing profound sorrow caused by the jewel of love. This emotional condition is depicted through the literary device of proverbial reference (*irsoli masal*).

In the seventh and eighth couplets of the ghazal, Nodira skillfully employs metaphor (*istiora*), antithesis (*tazod*), and proverbial allusion (*irsoli masal*) simultaneously. Expressions such as *morning-evening (subh-shom)* and *joy-sorrow (nashot-g'am)* create antithesis, while *the shining sun (xurshidi tobon)* symbolizes Umarxon through metaphor. In the eighth couplet, the expression referring to "the death of Solomon and the liberation of the demons" functions as a proverbial allusion (*irsoli masal*), whereas the reference to Prophet Solomon constitutes an allusion and metaphorical layer of meaning. In the closing couplet (*maqta'*) of the ghazal, we once again observe the use of two additional literary devices:

**Komila bulbul kabi to nola insho ayladim,
Navbahor o'tti, xazon o'ldi guliston oqibat.**

– In this couplet, the poetess compares herself to a nightingale (*bulbul*). Like a nightingale lamenting in sorrow, she states that she composed this poem in grief. In the following line, she likens the most meaningful and joyful days of her life to spring, while comparing her sorrowful moments to autumn. By placing spring and autumn in opposition, she creates antithesis (*tazod*). Furthermore, the seasons of spring and autumn are metaphorically associated with the stages of human life, thereby forming a simile (*tashbeh*). The poetess also skillfully employs the literary

device of semantic harmony (*tanosub*) through the use of related words such as *spring*, *nightingale*, and *rose garden* (*guliston*).

Having demonstrated an artistic and masterful application of *talmeh* throughout her works, the poetry of Nodira continues to be read with great interest by readers. This serves as clear evidence that the poetess's творчество has become one of the rare masterpieces of our classical literary heritage.

References:

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